

Photoexcited species localize on solvent-accessible fluorophore-rich domains inside carbon dots

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the optical properties of luminescent carbon dots (CDs) at the electronic level is essential for engineering their light-responsive behavior. The localization of photoexcited species and the pathways of their de-excitation govern CD performance in sensing, bioimaging, and emerging photocatalytic applications. Yet, the underlying mechanisms remain unresolved. Here, we combine multiscale simulations with experiments on CDs synthesized from citric acid (CA) and ethylenediamine (EDA), precursors capable of forming the molecular fluorophore 5-oxo-1,2,3,5-tetrahydroimidazo[1,2- α]pyridine-7-carboxylic acid (IPCA). All-atom molecular dynamics simulations in water reveal that CA-EDA oligomeric condensation products containing IPCA units spontaneously assemble into dynamic ~ 2 nm nanoparticles with amorphous internal structures and stacked domains reminiscent of those observed in transmission electron microscopy images of CDs. Time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT) calculations show that photoexcited carriers are generated in these domains and remain spatially distributed, not confined to the CD core. Quenching experiments with Hg^{2+} confirm their accessibility to the environment. We therefore propose a structural model of fluorophore-rich domains embedded in an amorphous carbonaceous matrix, explaining the quasi-spherical morphology and characteristic blue photoluminescence. This model provides a mechanistic basis for fluorescence sensing and photocatalysis and establishes a framework for rational design of CDs with tailored photophysical and catalytic properties.

1. Introduction

Carbon dots (CDs), discovered just over two decades ago, have rapidly matured into an important and widely studied class of carbon-based nanomaterials [1–4]. Their remarkable optical properties such as photoluminescence (PL), biocompatibility, together with facile, low-cost, and scalable synthesis boosted them into a wide spectrum of applications, ranging from bioimaging and sensing to optoelectronics and drug discovery [5,6]. Remarkably, the CD field continues to evolve with new application domains steadily emerging. Among them,

photocatalysis represents a particularly compelling frontier field, which was traditionally dominated by metal-containing semiconductors designed to optimize photoexcited charge generation and separation. Increasingly, CDs are being recognized as sustainable alternatives [7–11], owing to their composition from earth-abundant and light elements, and their facile, scalable synthesis. These attributes position CDs as attractive candidates for energy conversion and environmental remediation technologies [12,13]. Recent studies have demonstrated hydrogen generation rates exceeding $15.15 \text{ mmol}(\text{H}_2)\text{g}(\text{catalyst})^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$, and hydrogen peroxide photoproduction via polaron-mediated

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pathways, while sensing applications have achieved sensitive detection of toxic metal ions [14–17].

Nonetheless, the rational design and optimization of CDs for photocatalytic applications are still in their infancy. A key challenge lies in our limited understanding of the precise localization where the catalytically active sites reside in/on CDs, and how photoexcited charges localize within these structurally complex nanoparticles. Unlike well-defined crystalline semiconductors, CDs possess heterogeneous architectures encompassing multiple distinct categories: (i) core state CDs, where quantum confinement in nanosized sp^2 domains leads to size-dependent and often excitation-dependent PL; (ii) surface-state CDs, where PL originates from surface defects, heteroatom-induced trap states, or charge-transfer sites; and (iii) molecular-state CDs, where the emission stems from molecular fluorophores or cross-linked polymeric species formed during synthesis, resulting in excitation-independent PL [18–21]. Even modest variations in synthetic conditions like temperature, time, pH, and precursor stoichiometry can result in various structures of CDs, which significantly influence their electronic, optical, and catalytic properties [22–26]. This complexity hindered the use of CDs in the field of photocatalysis, rendering the elucidation of their structure-function relationships an ongoing and difficult endeavor [16, 27]. Specifically for catalysis, unresolved questions are the chemical identity and spatial localization of redox-active sites, and the degree of photoexcited charge separation across them [10,17,28].

Despite the inherent structural complexity and variability of CDs, several common features have been identified to rationalize their structural and optical behavior. A widely accepted structural model of a prototypical CD [29,30] comprises a sp^2 -hybridized carbon core surrounded by a shell rich in oxygen/nitrogen-containing functional groups [31]. The core-shell model explains water dispersibility and the appearance of PL of CDs [32]. Nevertheless, some CDs can be more accurately described by alternative structural models, such as carbonized-molecule or polymer models [33–41]. It has been also widely accepted that molecular fluorophores (MFs), especially IPCA molecule, can form during the bottom-up synthesis of CDs [38,42], and CDs themselves can undergo structural evolution from amorphous to crystalline nanoparticles (cf. Fig. 1) [43,44].

The structural and optical properties of CDs can be probed using a broad suite of experimental techniques. Complementary computational approaches are also well established in this field, providing indispensable insights into structural features of CDs at the atomic level [31,43, 45]. Ab-initio calculations elucidate reaction pathways leading to the formation of MFs and nucleation cores of CDs [46]. Classical molecular dynamics (MD) simulations reveal the dynamical behavior of CDs with graphitic cores [47] as well as interactions between MFs and CDs [35].

Time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT) calculations further resolve the electronic states responsible for absorption and emission spectra [48–52]. Together, these computational efforts highlight the indispensable role of theory in complementing experimental studies and, when integrated, provide deeper mechanistic understanding of CD formation, structure, and photophysics.

Here, we address the critical knowledge gap concerning the chemical identity and spatial localization of photoexcited states in CDs. Specifically, we focus on non-carbonized carbon dots (nc-CDs, Fig. 1) derived from the prototypical precursors citric acid (CA) and ethylenediamine (EDA). The polymerization, cyclization, IPCA formation, and assembly processes in this system have already been characterized in sufficient structural detail [46], enabling rigorous computational analysis. We employ classical all-atom MD simulations in explicit water solvent to resolve the dynamics of nc-CDs at femtosecond and atomic resolutions, localizing MFs and probing their accessibility to the solvent environment. TD-DFT calculations are further used to define the optical properties of nc-CDs and to identify and spatially map the photoexcited charge carriers. These computational findings are cross-validated through quenching experiments with Hg^{2+} ions. By integrating complementary computational and experimental approaches, we delineate both the chemical nature and spatial localization of excited states in nc-CDs. Beyond advancing fundamental understanding of CD formation and their photophysics, this work establishes a framework for the rational design of CDs tailored for efficient and selective photocatalysis.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Theoretical calculations

Models for MD simulations were derived by condensation of three CA and three EDA molecules (CA:EDA = 1:1) into short CA-EDA oligomers. This approach is based on our recent findings focused on early stages of CA-EDA derived CD formation prior the carbonization phase, where combination of quantum mechanical (QM) calculations, reactive MD simulations, NMR and MALDI-TOF measurements unraveled the reaction mechanism in the early stages [46]. Two sets of building blocks of short oligomers were considered (see Fig. 2a): i) EDA bound to CA via amide bonds formation through one A- and B-carboxylic groups in models A0-A2; and ii) EDA bound to CA through two B-carboxylic groups in models B0–B2 (see inset in Fig. 2a). A0(B0), A1(B1) and A2 (B2) represent three different protonation states of the oligomer, where zero, one or two $-COOH$ groups are deprotonated, respectively (net charge of 0, -1 and -2 per oligomer). Notably, the IPCA MF is formed during the hydrothermal reaction of CA and EDA, leading to all our

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of the bottom-up formation of CDs. Molecular precursors undergo polymerization, dehydration, and cyclization yielding oligomers and molecular fluorophores (MFs, smaller than 2 nm), which self-assemble into non-carbonized carbon dots (nc-CDs, ~2 nm). Further carbonization leads to the formation of larger (bigger than 2 nm) CDs with crystalline (graphite-like) cores.

Fig. 2. (a) CA-EDA oligomers which were used as building blocks of nc-CDs models. In (A0-A2), EDA is bound asymmetrically to CA via A- and B-carboxylic group (see inset in B0 panel), while in (B0-B2) it binds symmetrically via two B-carboxylic groups. Arrows point to the titratable site. (b) Representative snapshots from MD simulations of nc-CDs illustrating the assembled structures formed by ten CA-EDA oligomers in water.

models being capped with IPCA molecule [38]. Eventually, ten oligomers with a total molar mass of 6000 g mol^{-1} were placed in a $6 \times 6 \times 6 \text{ nm}$ cubic box for all MD simulations, and the formation of our modeled nc-CDs was computed. The summary of the executed MD simulations is shown in Table S1.

Classical all-atom MD simulations were considered to study dynamics, organization and aggregation processes of the oligomers. Topologies for MD simulations were set up with parameters from the Generalized Amber Force Field [53], and with our calculated RESP [54] partial charges (Fig. S1). These were determined using the Antechamber tool [55] from the Amber software package [56] by fitting of the electrostatic potential computed at the HF/6-31G* level in a gaseous state. After this parametrization, oligomers building blocks were added to a cubic simulation box and solvated with explicit TIP3P [57] water molecules. For MD simulation with Hg^{2+} ions, their non-bonded parameters were taken from the literature [58,59]. After an initial minimization, a two-step equilibration process was employed. The first step involved heating the system from 10 K to 300 K over 1 ns using a V-rescale [60] thermostat with a 0.1 ps time constant. This was followed by a 2 ns

equilibration of pressure using the isotropic Berendsen [61] barostat, keeping the pressure at 1 bar and maintaining the temperature at 300 K with a pressure relaxation time constant of 2 ps. Subsequently, the MD simulations were conducted for 100 ns in the NPT ensemble with a 2 fs time step. The bonds with hydrogens were constrained using the LINCS [62] algorithm. Temperature control was maintained at 300 K via the V-rescale thermostat with a 0.1 ps time constant, while pressure was regulated at 1 bar using the isotropic Parrinello-Rahman barostat with a 2 ps relaxation time. Electrostatic interactions were managed using the particle-mesh Ewald [63] method, applying a real-space cut-off of 1 nm, which was also used for van der Waals interactions. Periodic boundary conditions were applied in all directions of the $6 \times 6 \times 6 \text{ nm}$ simulation box. All the MD simulations were executed in Gromacs 5.0 [64].

To capture thermal effects of the molecules, selected structures from MD simulations were considered as input structures for the optical properties calculations at the TD-DFT level of theory. The vertical excitation energies (VEEs) were calculated employing different simplifications, due to size-related issues of the nc-CDs models. Three different approximations were considered; i) simplified time-dependent density

functional theory (sTD-DFT) [65] in ORCA6.0, [66] ii) TD-DFT in ORCA6.0 and iii) quantum mechanics/molecular mechanics (QM/MM) approach in Gaussian16 [67]. Benchmarking calculations with single IPCA molecule were carried out using sTD-DFT at ω B97X-D3/def2-SVP/SMD, and TD-DFT calculation at ω B97X-D3/def2-SV(P)/gas, ω B97X-D3/def2-TZVP/gas, and ω B97X-D3/def2-TZVP/CPCM(water). sTD-DFT methodology was further used for VEEs calculations of nc-CD models, which were constructed by extracting the assembled nc-CDs, excluding solvent, from several different simulation times of A0 model. These models are labeled as M1–M10 and summarized in Table S2. For all models except M4, a few oligomers were deleted from the starting structure to reduce the computational costs (Table S2). For these calculations, we set 5.0 eV energy threshold to calculate excited state levels. Furthermore, another set of benchmarking calculations validating sTD-DFT methodology for M1–M10 was carried out employing TD-DFT calculation (two excited states) at ω B97X-D3/def2-SV(P)/gas and/or CPCM(water) environment.

Concerning QM/MM calculations, the input geometries were extracted from the MD simulations. Then, TD-DFT/MM calculations with electrostatic embedding were performed using the ONIOM (Our own N-layered Integrated molecular Orbital molecular Mechanics) [68, 69] method as implemented in Gaussian 16. The excitation and emission energies were computed at the ω B97X-D/def2-TZVP [70] level of theory in the QM region and GAFF in the MM region. One or two CA-EDA oligomers were considered in the QM region due to the computational cost. This strategy was proven to provide reasonable outcomes in a previous study on the PL properties of IPCA molecules and their dimers [34]. Overall, for every assembly extracted from MD simulation at a specific time, 10 calculations were performed, where different CA-EDA oligomers were considered for the QM region. For the calculations of emission, during the QM/MM ONIOM optimizations of the S_1 excited state the energy contributions from the environment were approximated by the GS energy assuming localization of the electronic excitation in the model (QM) region [68].

Images were rendered in PyMOL (version 1.7.2.1) [71], and Avogadro (1.2.0.) [72]. Absorption and emission spectra were plotted using Chemcraft (version 1.8) [73]. Stacking analysis was performed using an in-house script, where an overlap of two projections of IPCA units into a plane was used to assess the appearance of IPCA stacking. Metrics describing the character of excitation were evaluated using Multiwfn [74,75].

2.2. Experimental methods

CDs were synthesized following the procedure reported by Pykal et al. [46] Briefly, CDs were synthesized hydrothermally by reacting citric acid monohydrate (1.05 g, 5.00 mmol) with ethylenediamine (0.334 mL) in 10 mL of deionized water at 180 °C for 10 h. Given the ratio of reactants and other synthetic conditions we employ, we aim to efficiently form IPCA fluorophores within the nc-CDs [46]. The UV–Vis absorption spectrum of the colloidal CDs was acquired on a Specord S600 spectrometer (Analytik Jena, Germany). Steady-state and time-resolved PL measurements were performed on FLS980 fluorescence spectrometer (Edinburgh Instruments) equipped with a 450 W xenon arc lamp and EPL-375 ps pulsed diode laser ($\lambda_{em} = 372$ nm, pulse width of 66.5 ps, a repetition rate of 10 MHz, and an average power of 75 μ W, Edinburgh Instruments) as the excitation sources.

3. Results and discussion

MD simulations reveal that self-assembled nc-CDs retain the typical quasi-spherical nanoparticle shape featuring a fluorophore core formed by stacks of IPCA molecules embedded in an amorphous matrix (as described later). The strongest assembly ability is observed when the oligomer building block has zero or one deprotonated COOH groups per oligomer (Fig. 2b, S2–S9), while charged models form significantly

smaller structures (Fig. 2b). Using a terminology borrowed from crystallization processes, the charged nc-CDs represent the nucleation sites of CDs, while the behavior of neutral models can be attributed to the maturation phase of CD formation.

The absolute interaction energy between different oligomers within the probed nc-CDs decreases with an increasing number of COOH deprotonations in both series of our model structures (Fig. S10a). This decrease is driven not only by the reduced Coulombic attraction between the species carrying the same charge, but also by a decreased Lennard-Jones (LJ) term describing dispersion/repulsion. The latter effect can be attributed to reduced contact between oligomers, arising from a looser structural organization and diminished formation of stacked IPCA/IPCA arrangements (vide infra).

The self-assembled globular aggregates reach a radius of around 2 nm (Fig. S11), which falls within the typical size range of CDs. The gyration radii analysis shows that the assembly process occurs within 20 ns for neutral models, with the gyration radii of A0 and B0 systems stabilizing at approximately 1.2 nm (Fig. 3a). Similarly, the A1 and B1 models also form compact, CD-like structures of similar size as neutral models within 70 ns simulation time. On the other hand, when two negatively charged carboxylate (COO^-) groups per oligomer are present, only loose aggregates are formed, which act as nucleation sites for CD growth. To further assess the shape of the assemblies, we compared the ratio of the surface area of a convex hull surrounding the formed nc-CDs to that of a circumscribed sphere. This analysis confirms that the A0 and A1 systems form the most spherical assemblies, while others exhibit more irregular shapes (Fig. S12). The compactness of the neutral and singly charged systems is also supported by hydrogen bond analysis (Fig. S13a), as it is observed that the average number of hydrogen bonds between interacting oligomers decrease with increasing deprotonation. This trend likely reflects hydrated structures with increasing negative charge, representing early-stage CD precursors.

A detailed analysis of the behavior of IPCA units bound on the CA-EDA oligomers reveals their strong tendency to adopt stacked configurations. Cluster size distribution analysis indicates that in the A0 and B0 neutral systems, IPCA units predominantly form trimers and octamers, respectively, throughout most of the simulation (Fig. 3b–S13b). In contrast, unstacked IPCA units are the most abundant species in charged systems. Nevertheless, stacked IPCA multimers still emerge even under net negative charge conditions, indicating a persistent propensity for aggregation. Interaction energy calculations between IPCA-only segments of different oligomers show that their association is primarily driven by dispersion contributions described by the LJ potential, with electrostatic contributions playing a minimal role (Fig. S10b). The similarity in the dispersion/repulsion contributions described by the LJ potential across all systems suggests that the presence of CA-EDA oligomer chains may disrupt ideal stacking geometries observed in isolated IPCA molecules [35]. This disruption likely alters the overall shape and structure of the modeled nc-CDs.

A closer examination of the ordering confirms the amorphous nature of the formed nc-CDs with the distinct IPCA-IPCA interaction. Radial distribution function (RDF) analysis of carbon atoms around a single oligomer shows no pronounced peaks in either of the studied models (Fig. 3c), indicating a lack of long-range order. This absence of distinct RDF peaks which are typically expected for fully carbonized CDs with a graphitic core (displayed in Fig. 3c) further supports the conclusion that the nc-CDs are amorphous. Furthermore, center-of-mass (COM) analysis between different IPCA units demonstrates a tendency for this MF to form stacked arrangements within the nc-CDs. Once established, these stacking interactions remain stable throughout the simulation (Fig. 3d, Fig. S14–S19). The COM analysis proposes a distinct interaction reminiscent of those observed in CDs with a graphitic core [47], signifying that these nc-CDs are likely to exhibit characteristic graphitic layering in transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images despite the amorphous nature of our modeled nc-CDs [76,77].

Further analysis unveils that IPCA units remain solvent-accessible

Fig. 3. (a) Running averages (window 1 ns) in time of gyration radii calculated for the different models of nc-CDs. For clarity, the curves in (a) are vertically offset by 0.5 nm increments in the order A0, A1, A2, B0, B1, B2. (b) Cluster analysis displaying a tendency of IPCA units within CA-EDA oligomers to form stacked formations. (c) Radial distribution function (RDF, averaged over the entire simulation time) illustrating the spatial distribution of carbon atoms (excluding those belonging to the reference oligomer) around a single oligomer within the formed nc-CDs. Insets: Structural model of A0 model of nc-CD and carbonized/graphitized CDs (Gr-CD). Gr-CD exhibits distinct graphitic structure and is used here as a representative of highly ordered CDs [47]. (d) Time evolution of COM-COM distances of one IPCA unit (denoted as MOL) with respect to the rest of IPCA units (in the A0 model). For clarity, the curves in (d) are vertically offset by 0.5 nm increments in the order MOL2–10.

within the nc-CD model, rather than being buried inside the nanoparticle. This conclusion is supported by two key observations: (i) RDF of water around the N–H group of the IPCA five-membered ring and (ii) hydrogen bond formation between this nitrogen and surrounding water molecules. As shown in Fig. S20, the RDF exhibits a pronounced peak around 0.2 nm, indicating that the N–H groups are positioned at the periphery of the CD and interact directly with the aqueous environment. This pronounced peak also underscores the hydrophilic nature of our nc-CD structures. In parallel, hydrogen bond analysis (Fig. S21) confirms that the N–H group forms persistent hydrogen bonds with water molecules throughout the simulation, further supporting the conclusion that IPCA units are solvent-exposed and thus readily accessible to various external species.

Investigation of the optical properties of the studied nc-CD models reveals that photoexcitation occurs across multiple spatially distinct IPCA units that remain accessible to the surrounding environment. Absorption spectra of M1–M10 models calculated with sTD-DFT ω B97X-D3/def2-SVP/SMD show blue-shift relative to the experimental data (Fig. 4a, S31), which can be attributed to the approximations inherent in the used computational methodology. To verify the position of absorption peaks and character of excitations within the probed nc-CDs resulting from the sTD-DFT calculations, we performed a benchmarking comparing (i) sTD-DFT and TD-DFT methodologies with a model of single IPCA molecule; (ii) sTD-DFT, TD-DFT and higher-level ω B97X-D3/def2-TZVP/MM with nc-CDs models. Briefly, benchmarking validates the suitability of sTD-DFT methodology and shows that the observed blue-shift in the absorption spectra mainly arises from the necessity to use a small basis set, as the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition computed with sTD-DFT ω B97X-D3/def2-SV(P) is blue-shifted by 25 nm when compared to TD-DFT ω B97X-D3/def2-TZVP/CPCM(water) (Fig. S37).

Focusing on M4 model, the calculated absorption spectrum exhibits a broad peak encompassing several bright $S_0 \rightarrow S_n$ ($n = 1-10$) electronic

transitions (Fig. 4a). The first excited state appears at 341 nm ($f = 0.022$), and the corresponding natural transition orbital (NTO) analysis indicates local excitation delocalized over three stacked IPCA units (Fig. 5b). $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transition ($\lambda_{\max} = 320$ nm, $f = 0.075$), $S_0 \rightarrow S_3$ ($\lambda_{\max} = 320$ nm, $f = 0.062$) and $S_0 \rightarrow S_4$ ($\lambda_{\max} = 318$ nm, $f = 0.066$) transitions exhibit partial charge transfer (CT) character due to IPCA interacting complexes. Importantly, the generation of photoexcited charge carriers occurs on different IPCA units which are spatially located in various spots within the nc-CDs. Additionally, other nc-CD models (M1–M3, M5–M10) reveal other characters of excitations (Fig. S22–S30), e.g., local excitation occurring on a single IPCA unit which is not involved in the favorable stacking (e.g., see S_4 in Fig. S24), or CT excitations involving three IPCA units within the nc-CDs (e.g., S_1 in Fig. S22). The average value of $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ excitonic transition calculated with sTD-DFT ω B97X-D3/def2-SVP/SMD level of theory for ten M1–M10 model systems is 333 nm (see respective values in Fig. 5b and S22–S30).

The coexistence of several spatially distributed optical centers, each originating from IPCA interacting complexes, represents a defining structural feature of these nc-CDs. For all excitations, photogenerated electron-hole pairs remain in close spatial proximity. This suggests that small nc-CDs are intrinsically more favorable for photoemission-related applications, where rapid recombination is advantageous, rather than for photocatalysis, which requires efficient charge separation. Enhanced photocatalytic activity could potentially be achieved either through targeted functionalization of the nc-CDs or by promoting further carbonization [17].

PL features of our nc-CD models support the findings that their optical properties originate from fluorophore centers. The calculated vertical emission energy reaches an average value of 384 nm. This represents a blue-shift relative to the experimentally observed emission around 444 nm for CA-EDA CDs (Fig. 4c). This discrepancy is not unexpected given the level of theory employed, as a similar deviation was

Fig. 4. (a) Calculated and experimental (dashed-dotted line) absorption spectra (normalized to the first absorption peak) of A0 systems calculated for structures sampled with the MD simulations. A0, A0-d were calculated using QM/MM ω B97X-D/def2-TZVP/GAFF level of theory with one (A0) or two (A0-d) IPCA units in the QM region. M4 was computed with sTD-DFT ω B97X-D3/def2-SVP/SMD. For calculated spectra, line spectra were convoluted by a Gaussian function assuming the inhomogeneous broadening of peaks with $\sigma = 20$ nm. (b) Calculated excitation-emission maps averaged over all the IPCA molecules within the A0 model. (c) Steady-state PL emission spectra of CDs in pure water and in the presence of different quenchers (1 ppm Pb²⁺, Cu²⁺, KI, and Hg²⁺). Inset: Representative snapshots showing an example how Hg²⁺ are captured by the surface of the A1 model (Hg²⁺ are in red, IPCA units in blue, rest of nc-CDs gray). (d) Selected PL decays for CDs in water (purple) and in the presence of Hg²⁺ (red), illustrating the pronounced PL lifetime shortening induced by Hg²⁺. Solid lines represent exponential fits used for PL lifetime extraction. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

previously reported for IPCA molecules non-covalently embedded in graphitic CDs [34]. Furthermore, a minor shift in excitation/emission energies may also arise from the structural modification of the IPCA moiety, i.e., the replacement of the COOH group, present in the stand-alone IPCA molecule, with CONH groups in the covalently integrated form [33]. Based on the computed excitation and emission energies and the corresponding oscillator strengths, we simulated the PL spectra of IPCA units distributed throughout the nc-CDs, and constructed excitation-emission maps. The simulated emission spectra demonstrate excitation-independent behavior (Fig. S32) and broad emission bands (Fig. S33), which have origin in several IPCA centers embedded in different parts of CDs. Such emission, arising from discrete molecular units that act as emissive centers, is characteristic of what is also referred to in the literature as molecular-state CDs [38,78]. Excitation-emission maps display blue shift of emission (Fig. 4b) in comparison to the experimentally measured maps, nonetheless, it can be concluded that the probed nc-CDs exhibit blue emission. These excitation-emission maps appear broader along the vertical (emission) axis (Fig. S34) compared to the experimental spectra; however, this can be attributed to the limited thermal averaging, constrained by the high computational cost of the computations. In summary, our proposed model of nc-CDs aligns with the distinctive blue PL observed in CA-EDA-based CDs.

Finally, the solvent accessibility of IPCA is confirmed by PL quenching experiments, revealing a diffusion-controlled interaction with Hg²⁺ ions (Fig. 4c and d). Under 100 ppm Hg²⁺, the steady-state PL spectrum is uniformly attenuated with essentially no spectral shift (Fig. 4c), indicating that the emissive IPCA centers remain intact and that quenching occurs via excited-state deactivation rather than chemical transformation or aggregation. Time-resolved PL further shows a reduction of the PL lifetime from $\tau = 15.0$ ns (water) to $\tau = 9.6$ ns (100

ppm Hg²⁺) (Fig. 4d). The near single-exponential decays imply a relatively uniform emissive population, consistent with Hg²⁺ interacting with solvent-exposed emissive centers [59]. Together, these observations demonstrate that the emissive states are not confined within the nc-CD interior but remain partially exposed to the solvent and dynamically accessible to molecular quenchers (Fig. 5a), in agreement with the computational model. Importantly, such surface-localized and accessible excited states are highly significant, as they provide direct interaction sites with diffusing redox species, which is a key mechanistic requirement for not only sensing applications, but eventually also for photocatalysis [15,16].

MD simulations with Hg²⁺ further substantiate these findings. Hg²⁺ ions preferentially interact with negatively charged carboxyl groups at the periphery of the nanoparticle (Fig. S35a and b). In the A2 model, which has the highest number of COO⁻ groups, Hg²⁺ ions tend to localize closest to oxygen atoms of IPCA units, maintaining consistently shorter distances ~ 0.4 nm compared to A0 and A1 models (Fig. 4c–S35a). Even closer contacts ~ 0.2 nm are observed with COO⁻ oxygen atoms, indicating effective capture of the Hg²⁺ ions from the solvent via non-covalent Hg²⁺–COO⁻ interaction (Fig. S36). The persistence of Hg²⁺ ions within 0.6 nm of IPCA unit's oxygen atoms, particularly in the A2 model, mirrors the quenching behavior seen experimentally, providing a direct structural basis for the detected PL suppression (Fig. S35b). Together, these experimental and computational results deliver compelling evidence that the bright centers in our CD model are solvent-accessible, functionally active, and positioned exactly as predicted, thus validating the structural framework proposed in this work.

Fig. 5. (a) Solvent accessible surface of assembled nc-CD models showing in blue IPCA units. (b) Natural transition orbitals displayed for the M4 model (see Table S2) taken from the MD simulation ($t = 55$ ns) of the A0 model, calculated with sTD-DFT ω B97X-D3/def2-SVP/SMD methodology. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

4. Conclusions

We combined MD simulations, TD-DFT calculations, and PL quenching experiments to resolve the spatial localization and chemical nature of photoexcited states in nc-CDs derived from CA and EDA precursors. Our findings demonstrate that emissive states originate from solvent-accessible, MF-rich domains formed by stacked IPCA units embedded within an amorphous matrix. These fluorophores remain partially exposed to the aqueous environment, as evidenced by both water-accessibility in simulations and Hg^{2+} -induced quenching in experiments, establishing that photoexcited species are not confined to the nanoparticle interior but instead dynamically accessible at the particle-solvent interface. This structural model explains the characteristic blue PL of CA-EDA nc-CDs and provides a mechanistic basis for their activity in interfacial processes. While the fluorescence originates from molecular IPCA units, the nanoscale-size assembly provides the structural rigidity and solvent accessibility necessary to stabilize these fluorophore-rich domains and sustain efficient emission. Importantly, the solvent accessibility of emissive domains positions these materials as promising platforms for applications where direct interaction with molecular or ionic species is required, including fluorescence-based sensing and photocatalysis. Beyond advancing fundamental understanding of CD photophysics, this integrated computational-experimental framework offers a generalizable approach for linking structural motifs to function, thereby enabling rational design of CDs tailored for efficient and selective energy and environmental technologies. We note, however, that the

systematic blue shift of the calculated absorption spectra relative to experiment indicates that, although qualitative trends and excited-state localization are captured, the employed theoretical framework does not yet provide quantitatively predictive excitation energies, motivating future methodological refinement.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Michal Langer: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Lukáš Zdražil:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Andrey L. Rogach:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology. **Silvio Osella:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Michal Otyepka:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: M.O. has a share in ATOMIVER, s.r.o. (Czechia) focused on the development of supercapacitor electrode materials. Other authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests that could have

appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2026.121228>. The datasets generated and/or analyzed during the current study are available in the Zenodo repository at <https://zenodo.org/records/18153982>.

References

- [1] F. Rigodanza, M. Burian, F. Arcudi, L. Dordević, H. Amenitsch, M. Prato, Snapshots into carbon dots formation through a combined spectroscopic approach, *Nat. Comm.* 12 (1) (2021) 2640.
- [2] Y. Wang, A. Hu, Carbon quantum dots: synthesis, properties and applications, *J. Mater. Chem. C* 2 (34) (2014) 6921–6939.
- [3] Y. Hu, O. Seivert, Y. Tang, H.E. Karahan, A. Bianco, Carbon dot synthesis and purification: trends, challenges and recommendations, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.* 63 (48) (2024) e202412341.
- [4] V. Torregrosa-Rivero, M. Rosell, J.I. Castro Castro, F. de la Cruz-Martínez, J. A. Castro-Osma, A. Lara-Sánchez, S. Nonell, J. García-Martínez, R. Bresolí-Obach, E. Serrano, C. Martín, Are carbon dots cluster-triggered luminogens? How through-space interaction arrangement influence the optical properties of carbon dots, *Carbon N. Y.* 243 (2025) 120540.
- [5] S.Y. Lim, W. Shen, Z. Gao, Carbon quantum dots and their applications, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 44 (1) (2014) 362–381.
- [6] H. Li, Z. Kang, Y. Liu, S.T. Lee, Carbon nanodots: synthesis, properties and applications, *J. Mater. Chem.* 22 (46) (2012) 24230–24253.
- [7] M. Han, S. Zhu, S. Lu, Y. Song, T. Feng, S. Tao, J. Liu, B. Yang, Recent progress on the photocatalysis of carbon dots: Classification, mechanism and applications, *Nano Today* 19 (2018) 201–218.
- [8] V. Agarwal, A. Chakraborty, A. Prasun, T.K. Sahu, T.K. Sarma, Carbon dots as versatile metal-free photocatalysts for organic transformations, *ChemCatChem* 17 (15) (2025) e00414.
- [9] S. Cailotto, M. Negrato, S. Daniele, R. Luque, M. Selva, E. Amadio, A. Perosa, Carbon dots as photocatalysts for organic synthesis: Metal-free methylene-oxygen-bond photocleavage, *Green Chem.* 22 (4) (2020) 1145–1149.
- [10] S. Macpherson, T. Lawson, A. Abfalterer, P. Andrich, A. Lage, E. Reisner, T. G. Euser, S.D. Stranks, A.S. Gentleman, Influence of electron donors on the charge transfer dynamics of carbon nanodots in photocatalytic systems, *ACS Catal.* 14 (16) (2024) 12006–12015.
- [11] D. Langford, Y. Reva, Y. Bo, K. Gubanov, M. Wu, A. Günay-Gürer, L.A. Mai, R. W. Crisp, I. Engelmann, E. Spiecker, R.H. Fink, A. Kahnt, B. Jana, D.M. Guldi, Improving photocatalytic hydrogen generation via polycyclic acid-based carbon nanodots, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.* 64 (13) (2025) e202418626.
- [12] N. Basavaraj, A. Sekar, R. Yadav, Review on green carbon dot-based materials for the photocatalytic degradation of dyes: fundamentals and future perspective, *Mater. Adv.* 2 (23) (2021) 7559–7582.
- [13] P.P. Debes, D. Schatz, Y. Aydogan-Sun, J.P. Martínez, M. Langer, J. Hessling, J. Gallego, E. Menna, B.M. Smarsly, M. Schönhoff, S. Osella, J. Wachtveitl, H. A. Wegner, T. Gatti, Covalent carbon nanodot-azobenzene hybrid photoswitches: the impact of meta/para connectivity and sp³ spacer on photophysical properties, *J. Mater. Chem. C* 13 (23) (2025) 11879–11889.
- [14] B. Jana, Y. Reva, T. Scharl, V. Strauss, A. Cadranel, D.M. Guldi, Carbon nanodots for all-in-one photocatalytic hydrogen generation, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 143 (48) (2021) 20122–20132.
- [15] L. Zdražil, Z. Bařura, M. Langer, S. Kalytchuk, D. Panáček, M. Scheibe, S. Kment, H. Kmentová, M.A. Thottappali, E. Mohammadi, M. Medved', A. Bakandritsos, G. Zoppellaro, R. Zbořil, M. Otyepka, Magnetic polaron states in photoluminescent carbon dots enable hydrogen peroxide photoproduction, *Small* 19 (32) (2023) 2206587.
- [16] L. Zdražil, A. Cadranel, M. Medved', M. Otyepka, R. Zbořil, D.M. Guldi, Designing carbon dots for enhanced photo-catalysis: challenges and opportunities, *Chem* 10 (9) (2024) 2700–2723.
- [17] L. Morbiato, L. Cardo, E. Sturabotti, P. Gobbo, G. Filippini, M. Prato, Structure matters: tailored graphitization of carbon dots enhances photocatalytic performance, *ACS Nano* 19 (4) (2025) 4887–4900.
- [18] M. Shamsipur, A. Barati, A.A. Taherpour, M. Jamshidi, Resolving the multiple emission centers in carbon dots: from fluorophore molecular states to aromatic domain states and carbon-core states, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 9 (15) (2018) 4189–4198.
- [19] A. Ghaffarkhah, E. Hosseini, M. Kamkar, A.A. Sehat, S. Dordanihaghghi, A. Allahbakhsh, C. Van Der Kuur, M. Arjmand, A. Ghaffarkhah, E. Hosseini, M. Kamkar, A.A. Sehat, S. Dordanihaghghi, M. Arjmand, A. Allahbakhsh, Synthesis, applications, and prospects of graphene quantum dots: a comprehensive review, *Small* 18 (2) (2022) 2102683.
- [20] S. Zhu, Y. Song, X. Zhao, J. Shao, J. Zhang, B. Yang, The photoluminescence mechanism in carbon dots (graphene quantum dots, carbon nanodots, and polymer dots): Current state and future perspective, *Nano Res.* 8 (2) (2015) 355–381.
- [21] P.P. Debes, M. Langer, M. Pagel, E. Menna, B. Smarsly, S. Osella, J. Gallego, T. Gatti, Functional groups accessibility and the origin of photoluminescence in N/O-containing bottom-up carbon nanodots, *ChemNanoMat* 10 (2) (2024) e202300471.
- [22] B.J. Moon, S.J. Kim, A. Lee, Y. Oh, S.K. Lee, S.H. Lee, T.W. Kim, B.H. Hong, S. Bae, Structure-controllable growth of nitrogenated graphene quantum dots via solvent catalysis for selective C-N bond activation, *Nat. Comm.* 12 (1) (2021) 5879.
- [23] A. Cadranel, J.T. Margraf, V. Strauss, T. Clark, D.M. Guldi, Carbon nanodots for charge-transfer processes, *Acc. Chem. Res.* 52 (4) (2019) 955–963.
- [24] S.Y. Song, K.K. Liu, Q. Cao, X. Mao, W.B. Zhao, Y. Wang, Y.C. Liang, J.H. Zang, Q. Lou, L. Dong, C.X. Shan, Ultraviolet phosphorescent carbon nanodots, *Light Sci. Appl.* 11 (1) (2022) 146.
- [25] H. Pei, Z. Zhang, M. Ouyang, H. Liang, J. Liu, S. Li, H. Zhang, Y. Qi, L. Wei, C. Liu, L. Shi, R. Guo, N. Liu, Z. Mo, Chiral carbonized polymer dots: a comprehensive review, *SM&T* 43 (2025) e01271.
- [26] E. Giuliani, M. Sbacchi, S. Agostini, G. Filippini, B. Bartolomei, P. Gobbo, M. Prato, Molecular insights into the formation and functionalization of carbon nanodots: from precursor intermediates to surface chemistry quantification, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.* (2025) e202515073.
- [27] K.J. Mintz, M. Bartoli, M. Rovere, Y. Zhou, S.D. Hettiarachchi, S. Paudyal, J. Chen, J.B. Domena, P.Y. Liyanage, R. Sampson, D. Khadka, R.R. Pandey, S. Huang, C. C. Chusuei, A. Tagliaferro, R.M. Leblanc, A deep investigation into the structure of carbon dots, *Carbon N. Y.* 173 (2021) 433–447.
- [28] B.C.M. Martindale, G.A.M. Hutton, C.A. Caputo, S. Prantl, R. Godin, J.R. Durrant, E. Reisner, Enhancing light absorption and charge transfer efficiency in carbon dots through graphitization and core nitrogen doping, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.* 56 (23) (2017) 6459–6463.
- [29] L. Dordević, F. Arcudi, M. Cacioppo, M.A. Prato, Multifunctional chemical toolbox to engineer carbon dots for biomedical and energy applications, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 17 (2) (2022) 112–130.
- [30] H. Wang, L. Ai, Z. Song, M. Nie, J. Xiao, G. Li, S. Lu, Surface modification functionalized carbon dots, *Chem. Eur J.* 29 (65) (2023) e202302383.
- [31] M. Langer, M. Paloncýová, M. Medved', M. Pykal, D. Nachtigallová, B. Shi, A.J. Aquino, H. Lischka, M. Otyepka, Progress and challenges in understanding of photoluminescence properties of carbon dots based on theoretical computations, *Appl. Mater. Today* 22 (2021) 100924.
- [32] S. Wei, X. Yin, H. Li, X. Du, L. Zhang, Q. Yang, R. Yang, Multi-color fluorescent carbon dots: graphitized sp² conjugated domains and surface state energy level co-modulate band gap rather than size effects, *Chem. Eur J.* 26 (36) (2020) 8129–8136.
- [33] M. Langer, L. Zdražil, M. Medved', M. Otyepka, Communication of molecular fluorophores with other photoluminescence centres in carbon dots, *Nanoscale* 15 (8) (2023) 4022–4032.
- [34] M. Langer, T. Hrivnák, M. Medved', M. Otyepka, Contribution of the molecular fluorophore IPCA to excitation-independent photoluminescence of carbon dots, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 125 (22) (2021) 12140–12148.
- [35] M. Langer, M. Paloncýová, M. Medved', M. Otyepka, Molecular fluorophores self-organize into C-Dot seeds and incorporate into C-Dot structures, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 11 (19) (2020) 8252–8258.
- [36] N.V. Tepliakov, E.V. Kundelev, P.D. Khavlyuk, Y. Xiong, M.Y. Leonov, W. Zhu, A. V. Baranov, A.V. Fedorov, A.L. Rogach, I.D. Rukhlenko, sp²-sp³-hybridized atomic domains determine optical features of carbon dots, *ACS Nano* 13 (9) (2019) 10737–10744.
- [37] L. Vallan, H. Imahori, Citric acid-based carbon dots and their application in energy conversion, *ACS Appl. Electron. Mater.* 4 (9) (2022) 4231–4257.
- [38] Y. Song, S. Zhu, S. Zhang, Y. Fu, L. Wang, X. Zhao, B. Yang, Investigation from chemical structure to photoluminescent mechanism: A type of carbon dots from the pyrolysis of citric acid and an amine, *J. Mater. Chem. C Mater.* 3 (23) (2015) 5976–5984.
- [39] D.A. Sousa, M.N. Berberan-Santos, J.V. Prata, Are “carbon dots” always carbon dots? Evidence for their supramolecular nature from structural and dynamic studies in solution and in the pure solid, *Chem. Eur J.* 30 (3) (2024) e202302955.
- [40] L. Vallan, E.P. Urriolabeitia, F. Ruipérez, J.M. Matxain, R. Canton-Vitoria, N. Tagmatarchis, A.M. Benito, W.K. Maser, Supramolecular-enhanced charge transfer within entangled polyamide chains as the origin of the universal blue

- fluorescence of polymer carbon dots, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 140 (40) (2018) 12862–12869.
- [41] S. Zhu, Y. Song, J. Shao, X. Zhao, B. Yang, Non-conjugated polymer dots with crosslink-enhanced emission in the absence of fluorophore units, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.* 54 (49) (2015) 14626–14637.
- [42] Y. Xiong, J. Schneider, E.V. Ushakova, A.L. Rogach, Influence of molecular fluorophores on the research field of chemically synthesized carbon dots, *Nano Today* 23 (2018) 124–139.
- [43] X. Zhao, J. Wei, T. Song, Z. Wang, D. Yang, X. Zhang, F. Huo, Y. Zhang, H.M. Xiong, Computational insights into carbon dots: Evolution of structural models and structure–activity relationships, *Chem. Eng. J.* 481 (2024) 148779.
- [44] L. Cao, M. Zan, F. Chen, X. Kou, Y. Liu, P. Wang, Q. Mei, Z. Hou, W.F. Dong, L. Li, Formation mechanism of carbon dots: From chemical structures to fluorescent behaviors, *Carbon N. Y.* 194 (2022) 42–51.
- [45] F. Mocci, L.D.V. Engelbrecht, C. Olla, A. Cappai, M.F. Casula, C. Melis, L. Stagi, A. Laaksonen, C.M. Carbonaro, Carbon nanodots from an in silico perspective, *Chem. Rev.* 122 (16) (2022) 13709–13799.
- [46] M. Pykal, J. Nociarová, D. Řeha, J. Filo, M. Šebela, P. Zajíček, M. Paloncýová, C. Olla, F. Mocci, A. Cappai, C.M. Carbonaro, Z. Bařura, L. Zdražil, R. Zbořil, A. L. Rogach, M. Medved', M. Otyepka, Thermodynamics and kinetics of early stages of carbon dot formation: A case of citric acid and ethylenediamine reaction, *Nanoscale* 17 (13) (2025) 7780–7789.
- [47] M. Paloncýová, M. Langer, M. Otyepka, Structural dynamics of carbon dots in water and N, N-dimethylformamide probed by all-atom molecular dynamics simulations, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 14 (4) (2018) 2076–2083.
- [48] H. Ding, X.H. Li, X.B. Chen, J.S. Wei, X.B. Li, H.M. Xiong, Surface states of carbon dots and their influences on luminescence, *J. Appl. Phys.* 127 (23) (2020) 231101.
- [49] W. Kasprzyk, S. Bednarz, P. Zmudzki, M. Galica, D. Bogdał, Novel efficient fluorophores synthesized from citric acid, *RSC Adv.* 5 (44) (2015) 34795–34799.
- [50] W. Kasprzyk, T. Świergosz, S. Bednarz, K. Walas, N.V. Bashmakova, D. Bogdał, Luminescence phenomena of carbon dots derived from citric acid and urea—a molecular insight, *Nanoscale* 10 (29) (2018) 13889–13894.
- [51] F. Siddique, M. Langer, M. Paloncýová, M. Medved', M. Otyepka, D. Nachtigalova, H. Lischka, A.J.A. Aquino, Conformational behavior and optical properties of a fluorophore dimer as model of luminescent centers in carbon dots, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 124 (26) (2020) 14327–14337.
- [52] M. Sudolská, M. Dubecký, S. Sarkar, C.J. Reckmeier, R. Zbořil, A.L. Rogach, M. Otyepka, Nature of absorption bands in oxygen-functionalized graphitic carbon dots, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 119 (23) (2015) 13369–13373.
- [53] J. Wang, R.M. Wolf, J.W. Caldwell, P.A. Kollman, D.A. Case, Development and testing of a general Amber force field, *J. Comput. Chem.* 25 (9) (2004) 1157–1174.
- [54] J. Wang, P. Cieplak, P.A. Kollman, How well does a restrained electrostatic potential (RESP) model perform in calculating conformational energies of organic and biological molecules? *J. Comput. Chem.* 21 (12) (2000) 1049–1074.
- [55] J. Wang, W. Wang, P.A. Kollman, D.A. Case, Automatic atom type and bond type perception in molecular mechanical calculations, *J. Mol. Graph. Model.* 25 (2) (2006) 247–260.
- [56] D.A. Case, T.A. Darden, T.E. Cheatham III, C.L. Simmerling, J. Wang, R.E. Duke, R. Luo, R.C. Walker, W. Zhang, K.M. Merz, B. Roberts, B. Wang, S. Hayik, A. Roitberg, G. Seabra, I. Kolossváry, K.F. Wong, F. Paesani, J. Vanicek, J. Liu, X. Wu, S.R. Brozell, T. Steinbrecher, H. Gohlke, Q. Cai, X. Ye, J. Wang, M.J. Hsieh, G. Cui, D.R. Roe, D.H. Mathews, M.G. Seetin, C. Sagui, V. Babin, T. Luchko, S. Gusarov, A. Kovalenko, P.A. Kollman, Amber 11, University of California, San Francisco, 2010.
- [57] W.L. Jorgensen, J. Chandrasekhar, J.D. Madura, R.W. Impey, M.L. Klein, Comparison of simple potential functions for simulating liquid water, *J. Chem. Phys.* 79 (2) (1983) 926–935.
- [58] Z. Li, S. Bhowmik, L. Sagresti, G. Brancato, M. Smith, D.E. Benson, P. Li, K.M. Merz, Simulating metal-imidazole complexes, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 20 (15) (2024) 6706–6716.
- [59] L. Zdražil, D. Panáček, V. Šedajová, Z. Bařura, M. Langer, M. Medved', M. Paloncýová, M. Scheibe, S. Kalytchuk, G. Zoppellaro, Š. Kment, A. Bakandritsos, M. Otyepka, R. Zbořil, A. Cadranel, D.M. Guldi, Carbon dots enabling parts-per-billion sensitive and ultrasensitive photoluminescence lifetime-based sensing of inorganic Mercury, *Ad. Opt. Mater.* (2023) 2300750.
- [60] G. Bussi, D. Donadio, M. Parrinello, Canonical sampling through velocity rescaling, *J. Chem. Phys.* 126 (1) (2007) 014101.
- [61] H.J.C. Berendsen, J.P.M. Postma, W.F. van Gunsteren, A. DiNola, J.R. Haak, Molecular dynamics with coupling to an external bath, *J. Chem. Phys.* 81 (8) (1984) 3684–3690.
- [62] B. Hess, H. Bekker, H.J.C. Berendsen, J.G.E.M. Fraaije, LINCS: A Linear constraint solver for molecular simulations, *J. Comput. Chem.* 18 (12) (1997) 1463–1472.
- [63] T. Darden, D. York, L. Pedersen, Particle mesh Ewald: An N-log(N) method for Ewald sums in large systems, *J. Chem. Phys.* 98 (12) (1993) 10089–10092.
- [64] D. Van Der Spoel, E. Lindahl, B. Hess, G. Groenhof, A.E. Mark, H.J.C. Berendsen, GROMACS: fast, flexible, and free, *J. Comput. Chem.* 26 (16) (2005) 1701–1718.
- [65] C. Bannwarth, S. Grimme, A simplified time-dependent density functional theory approach for electronic ultraviolet and circular dichroism spectra of very large molecules, *Comput. Theor. Chem.* 1040 (2014) 45–53.
- [66] F. Neese, The ORCA Program System, *Comput. Mol. Sci.* 2 (1) (2012) 73–78.
- [67] M.J. Frisch, G.W. Trucks, H.B. Schlegel, G.E. Scuseria, M.A. Robb, J.R. Cheeseman, G. Scalmani, V. Barone, G.A. Petersson, H. Nakatsuji, X. Li, M. Caricato, A.V. Marenich, J. Bloino, B.G. Janesko, R. Gomperts, B. Mennucci, H.P. Hratchian, J.V. Ortiz, A.F. Izmaylov, J.L. Sonnenberg, D. Williams-Young, F. Ding, F. Lipparini, F. Egidi, J. Goings, B. Peng, A. Petrone, T. Henderson, D. Ranasinghe, V.G. Zakrzewski, J. Gao, N. Rega, G. Zheng, W. Liang, M. Hada, M. Ehara, K. Toyota, R. Fukuda, J. Hasegawa, M. Ishida, T. Nakajima, Y. Honda, O. Kitao, H. Nakai, T. Vreven, K. Throssell, J.A. Montgomery Jr., J.E. Peralta, F. Ogliaro, M.J. Bearpark, J. J. Heyd, E.N. Brothers, K.N. Kudin, V.N. Staroverov, T.A. Keith, R. Kobayashi, J. Normand, K. Raghavachari, A.P. Rendell, J.C. Burant, S.S. Iyengar, J. Tomasi, M. Cossi, J.M. Millam, M. Klene, C. Adamo, R. Cammi, J.W. Ochterski, R.L. Martin, K. Morokuma, O. Farkas, J.B. Foresman, D.J. Fox, Gaussian16, Revision B.01, Wallingford CT, 2016.
- [68] L.W. Chung, W.M.C. Sameera, R. Ramozzi, A.J. Page, M. Hatanaka, G.P. Petrova, T. V. Harris, X. Li, Z. Ke, F. Liu, H.B. Li, L. Ding, K. Morokuma, The ONIOM method and its applications, *Chem. Rev.* 115 (2015) 5678–5796.
- [69] T. Vreven, K. Morokuma, On the application of the IMOMO (Integrated Molecular Orbital + Molecular Orbital) method, *J. Comput. Chem.* 21 (16) (2000) 1419–1432.
- [70] J. Da Chai, M. Head-Gordon, Long-range corrected hybrid density functionals with damped atom-atom dispersion corrections, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 10 (44) (2008) 6615–6620.
- [71] L.L.C. Schrodinger, The Pymol Molecular Graphics System, Version 1.7, 2015.
- [72] M.D. Hanwell, D.E. Curtis, D.C. Lonie, T. Vandermeersch, E. Zurek, G. R. Hutchison, Avogadro: An advanced semantic chemical editor, visualization, and analysis platform, *J. Cheminform.* 4 (8) (2012) 1–17.
- [73] G.A. Zhurko, D.A. Zhurko, Chemcraft. Version 1.8. www.chemcraftprog.com.
- [74] T. Lu, F. Chen, Multiwfn: A multifunctional wavefunction analyzer, *J. Comput. Chem.* 33 (2012) 580–592.
- [75] T. Lu, A comprehensive electron wavefunction analysis toolbox for chemists, *Multiwfn, J. Chem. Phys.* 161 (2024) 082503.
- [76] B. Bartolomei, M. Prato, The importance of the purification step and the characterization of the products in the synthesis of carbon nanodots, *Small* 19 (31) (2023) 2206714.
- [77] J.B. Essner, J.A. Kist, L. Polo-Parada, G.A. Baker, Artifacts and errors associated with the ubiquitous presence of fluorescent impurities in carbon nanodots, *Chem. Mater.* 30 (6) (2018) 1878–1887.
- [78] J. Schneider, C.J. Reckmeier, Y. Xiong, M. Von Seckendorff, A.S. Susha, P. Kasak, A.L. Rogach, Molecular fluorescence in citric acid-based carbon dots, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 121 (3) (2017) 2014–2022.